

IMPERIAL

Beyond Open Research II

Developing a proof-of-concept for quality and reliability

Summary of findings

Work Package 1

Data Transparency and Quality in the Context of Team Science

Workshop 1: Embedding Transparency and Quality in Research Data at the

LMS, 28 April 2025

"Highway to hell" and "Stairway to heaven" exercise: what holds you down (rocks) and what lifts you up (balloons) in the different stages of the research data management lifecycle?

Example practical activity from the Reproducibility by Design toolkit: participants identified the quality-critical steps in their research process and how to manage risks to quality at those stages

Barriers and incentives to research quality and transparency in the different stages of the research data management lifecycle

Planning and project set up

Barriers: Lack of knowledge, experience and confidence; resistance to data sharing; discipline-specificities and time constraints

Enablers: More training opportunities for students and staff; a scheme of data management champions; shared college-wide infrastructure and a standard directory

Data collection

Barriers: Technical and digital obsolescence and data storage capacity; lack of standards (e.g. file naming) and untried/unchecked data quality

Enablers: More human resources (permanent lab manager); procedures for handing over data when someone leaves the post; shared folder best practices for trustworthiness and reliability of data

Data processing and analysis

Barriers: Paper-based record keeping practices; lack of confidence when dealing with large datasets

Enablers: Peer-reviewing; domain-specific data stewards

Data archiving and sharing

Barriers: Password protected data, corrupted data, inaccessible data; the cost of data maintenance; not knowing the provenance of the data

Enablers: Accountability; transparency in the University policies for data archiving and sharing

Data discovery and reuse

Barriers: Balancing the need to release the data in a reasonable amount of time and following protocols and best practices; keeping data annotated, using URI and/or universally recognised ID's.

Enablers: Paying for patients' data copyright.

Feasibility of Adopting Data Management Plans (DMPs) for All New Starters (2025/26)

- Adoption *is feasible*, provided there is strengthened institutional support, consistent **training** and **standardised procedures** and *necessary* due to gaps in **knowledge, experience and confidence** among new researchers
- **Time constraints** were identified as a barrier and should be factored into implementation planning
- Embedding **peer-review** into the DMP process would allow to both develop skills and enhance research quality

Training, Support and Infrastructure for Data Transparency and Openness

- A robust **support ecosystem, encompassing technical, human and governance**, is essential to foster research quality, transparency and openness
- **Training** must be **ongoing and tailored to disciplinary needs**, particularly where confidentiality and privacy requirements affect data sharing
- Emphasis on developing clear **protocols** (e.g. file naming conventions, data handover procedures and metadata annotation)

Scrutiny of Data Types and Workflow Integration

- Effective scrutiny relies on transparent **protocols** and methodologies as well as trustworthy systems
- Well-trained **data stewards with domain expertise** can help address challenges such as data readiness and unclear processing strategies
- **Peer review** is recommended as a quality assurance measure

Recognition and Incentivisation of Good RDM Practice

- Incentives must reflect the **diverse** roles, including technical and support staff
- Additional **human resources** are essential to ensure research quality and transparency. This includes funding for roles such as **data stewards** and **peer reviewers** and, in some cases, covering copyright costs for data owners
- **Accountability** for both Principal Investigators and those involved in data archiving is key for good RDM practice

The workshop was an effective learning platform for the FAIR principles, successfully raising awareness of the benefits of transparent research in enhancing research quality.

However, the extent of improvement observed highlights the importance of continuing these conversations with already engaged participants, while also expanding the dialogue to include new and less-engaged audiences.

Work Package 2

Public and Patient Involvement in the Context of Fundamental Research and Team Science

Workshop 3: Improving Quality and Reliability by Involving the Public in Fundamental Research, 10 July 2025

Icebreaker: Turn to the person next to you, introduce yourself, explain the reason why you came to this workshop and tell them an interesting fact about yourself. Visually represent what your partner says.

Motivations for public involvement in fundamental research

Impact

Public partners emphasised the aspirational, altruistic side of impact: “Helping others is rewarding on itself.” Imperial community wants to be sure that research matters for their patients, to understand the audience better and enhance representativeness/representation.

Curiosity and learning

To understand research at Imperial and how public money is being used. The opportunity to ask questions directly to experts.

Bringing the public in is an opportunity to improve research by learning from lived experience, to understand ethical issues and public perception of “how acceptable the things we do in research are to the public” and to practice means of making data and outputs accessible to non-expert audiences.

Collaboration and communication

Public members noted that meaningful involvement can change the researcher’s approach to the project. Imperial staff values the possibility of getting new ideas from the public as well as more knowledge about their needs and how to reach them. Public engagement will also help in fine tuning research question and prevent from getting bogged down in narrow pathways.

Motivations’ codes	No. of occurrences
Collaboration and communication	13
Curiosity and learning	14
Enjoyment and creativity	4
Impact	16
Involvement and engagement	11
Personal benefit	8
Representation and inclusion	7
Transparency and trust	9

Public involvement in different stages of the research lifecycle

Partner
New outreach areas (libraries, community leaders, etc.)
Finding funds from public sector
Finding partners for the next phase to design the project
Enhance diversity of voices
Community members could help identifying involvement groups

Design
Ensuring inclusivity during the project
Understanding what public/patient consent to
Making sure the study is relevant
Go to public communities, explain in lay terms and accessible images
Understand public views on proposed design and question other ways to improve methods
Public contribution: their thoughts and priorities
Create vested interest early will help on dissemination
<i>"Speed-dating" for science-public relationships</i>
Understand what part of a condition to focus on
Gather lived experience

Act
Policy making
Participants to evaluate their experience
Determine what happened as a result of dissemination
Learning how to do things better next time
Improved feedback
Create more interest for further research

Collect
Transparency is important for the public to know What/why/when/who has access (e.g., insurance companies, GDPR)
Go to the public and consider their individual needs
Advertising effectively and via relevant routes
Providing training to gather data (qualitative and quantitative)
Designing questionnaire
Bringing those communities to the lab to understand the context
Data collection from as diverse parts of population as possible

Disseminate
Ensuring participants receive results of research
Ensuring results are in clear, lay language for non experts
Taking advices from participants where to disseminate results/findings
<i>'Question time' for science</i>
Understand barriers to sharing that may be unethical
Recognition for those involved
Create forums like this workshop

Analyse
Having good reliable info from patients will help to understand data
Members of public in Data Monitoring Committees
Preventing bias (parity in terms of collection + analysis)
Transparency: outreach activities to try data analysis

I found this workshop very stimulating, and has re-ignited my insatiable thirst for knowledge- I would very much welcome the opportunity to engage and contribute further to 'Open Research', and research more generally. Thank you for a very interesting day!

Learned: That involvement should be fun

Liked: Hearing from so many people

Ongoing, formative and responsive evaluation enabled immediate implementation of participants' suggestions to improve the workshop: "Would have liked if discussions Q's were provided written". The number and quality of feedback also increased in comparison to post-workshop surveys.

Lacked: BAME (black, Asian, ethnic minority) scientists/research

Longer for: **More time** for discussion

Work Package 3

Collaboration on Recognition and Incentives

Workshop 2: Using the SCOPE framework to recognise quality, reliability and

Team science, 5 June 2025

Outcomes of a practical activity involving a series of poorly compiled instructions for drawing SpongeBob SquarePants, where quality-critical steps were not properly documented. The game was a fun way to explore a serious problem of lack of reproducibility.

	RECOGNITION	KNOWLEDGE SHARING	TRAINING	DIVERSITY
OPTIONS	Require all members to have an ORCID	Create a skills database with regular updates and monitoring	Mandatory training (e.g., diversity, mental health), CPD every 6 years	Track diversity in roles, backgrounds, and outputs
	Acknowledge mentoring, teaching, supervision , considering personal circumstances	Track time spent sharing skills (e.g., via PDR)	Use of PRES (Postgraduate Research Experience Survey) and departmental surveys	Use HR systems and databases
	Award schemes for excellence in extra activities	Conduct anonymous staff surveys on collaboration	Collect demographic data to assess diversity and inclusion	Leverage external databases
	Include extra activities in performance reviews	Record training sessions/workshops attended or led	Combine quantitative (attendance) and qualitative (feedback) data	Promote public engagement
	Use a merit/credit taxonomy	Offer recognition prizes	Implement evaluation mechanisms	Use ORCID and Symplectic to track contributions
	Employ AI for credit attribution	Include skill-sharing in promotion criteria or job descriptions	Introduce scaffolded training from early stages	
	Promote licensing awareness and a culture of giving credit		Encourage peer mentoring and peer observation	
	Ensure transparent division of responsibilities		Use external auditors	
		Conduct Annual Review Conversations (ARC)		
PROBE	Risk of preferential treatment and unconscious bias	Tech-phobia, overstated contributions, database reliability	Survey fatigue and pressure on already busy staff	Gaming metrics by inflating role diversity
	Need for transparency and rigorous processes	Overburdening of junior staff, carers, part-time workers	Non-representative feedback	Privacy issues in HR data
	Potential over-reliance on AI	Low survey response rates and inaccuracy	Career risks tied to demographic disclosures	Security risks with external data
	Challenges in clearly attributing responsibilities	Time cost of training and sharing	Time-intensive data collection	Incomplete capture of outputs
	Ensuring equity in recognition across roles and circumstances	Risk of bias in recognition or exclusion of certain staff groups	Ineffective evaluations if not well-designed	Overemphasis on diversity at the expense of research quality
		One-size-fits-all training may not suit all roles	Role model fatigue among underrepresented groups	
		Bias in student feedback		

What aspects of the workshop contributed to making it useful, meaningful and accessible to you?

What held you back during this workshop?

I wish we had more PI representation though

Not having a clear definition of team science

We didn't have research group leaders such as PIs attending, so I felt we lacked thoughts from this pivotal group of colleagues.

Co-created definition of Team Science:

Team Science is a collective and collaborative approach to research that is enabled by knowledge-sharing, training, diversity and recognition.

Quality and reliability are mutually reinforcing, interdependent values that can be promoted through training and sustained by transparency.

Training is a key driver of research quality. It is instrumental to improve data management practices and can significantly strengthen public involvement, provided community members are equipped to support researchers. Moreover, it is a value in Team Science that benefits both trainees and educators. Looking ahead, training must be approached in an integrated manner, taking into consideration the needs of different stakeholders involved in research. ERC's knowledge and experience on Data Management plans and practices must be shared with PhD students. DMP peer-reviewing can be a formative exercise, on the one hand, and a quality and reliability enabler, on the other. Public members can learn from researchers the tools to be involved in research. Likewise, learning from community members' lived experience can benefit research impact.

Transparency of methods and data is essential for ensuring data reproducibility and it is a prerequisite for research reliability. Meaningful public involvement depends on transparent communication of project aims and scope and recognition relies on transparent accreditation. As a quality and reliability enabler, transparency must have a central role in all stages of the research lifecycle, encompassing training, assessment and public involvement.

Workshops format: Building on the BOR I workshop model, with well-briefed introductory talks from subject experts and facilitated breakout discussions, BOR II further explored participants involvement and agency. The use of toolkits and frameworks, as well as the tailoring of fit-to-purpose engagement activities for each workshop, contributed to adding a practical, co-creative approach to the discussion led format. Active participation in developing the tools, such as process mapping or values sitting and probing, paired collective critical thinking with horizontal decision making and resulted in actionable outputs.

Workshop evaluation: Built-in, ongoing evaluation (4 L's – liked, lacked, learned, longed template) proved effective and constructive. By allowing participants to give immediate feedback during the workshop, it was possible to have a more granular and comprehensive understanding of the participants' needs and to respond to their requirements as the workshop unfolded.

Record keeping, data analysis and sharing findings: Changes in record keeping methods, from note-taking in BOR I to collective documentation in BOR II, promoted dynamic participation and tangible results. Although the data collected is less structured, these materials enable more engaging ways of sharing the project findings.

Proof of concept for quality and reliability

Is feasible and necessary

Requires ongoing, tailored, discipline-specific training

Benefits from peer review to foster critical thinking and transparency

Public Involvement in Fundamental Research

There are ideas to explore (e.g. question time for science), but it is necessary to further investigate the specificities of involvement in fundamental research

What do we value in Team Science?

Diversity

Knowledge sharing

Recognition

Training

Options?

Diversity & Recognition:

Track contributors and their roles using ORCID

Training & Knowledge sharing:

Cross training demands with available skills

Methodological learnings

Discussion-driven, practical approach: *frameworks* and *templates* such as [Reproducibility by design](#), ALCOA and [SCOPE](#) are effective and appreciated.

The impact of the process: ongoing community building/strengthening around Open Research quality and reliability create the necessary systemic changes in Research Culture.

Next steps

- **Maintain BOR community involved and engage with new stakeholders, by developing a communication and engagement plan**
- **Engage with Principal Investigators and Heads of Departments**
- **Embed DMP peer-review as both training tool and quality and reliability assurance mechanism**
- **Collaborate with on-going projects at LMS that can provide a concrete context to apply and test public involvement practices**